

Research Briefing

Fragile Leadership Pipeline: Why Middle Leaders Want to Leave

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This Research Briefing combines quantitative data on turnover intentions among middle leaders in Scotland's schools with their own explanations of what motivates them to consider leaving their roles voluntarily (excluding retirement).

Key findings at a glance

- 77% of Principal Teachers in the 2024 Teacher Workload Research Project had considered leaving the profession in the past two years
- Four main factors drive departure intentions: prolonged working hours, challenging student conduct, difficult parental engagement, and complex learner needs with insufficient support
- Working hours are unsustainable: Teachers work 46 hours during weekdays - 11 hours above their contracted 35 hours, with many taking work home most nights
- Health impacts are severe: 22% cited work-related stress as a factor in considering leaving, with physical health problems including chronic stress, sleep disruption, and exhaustion
- Student behaviour challenges are escalating ranging from daily low-level disruption to serious incidents including aggression and verbal abuse
- Middle leaders note difficulties in parental relationships, citing unrealistic expectations, strained communications, and reduced trust in their professional expertise
- Resource pressures are intensifying: schools report increasingly complex student needs alongside significant reductions in support staff (halved in some cases), affecting middle leaders' ability to provide desired levels of support
- Middle leaders function as "institutional dampeners" - absorbing pressures from multiple directions while protecting classroom teachers
- Those who had not considered leaving and intend to stay (23%) are motivated by: passion for teaching, positive student relationships, and job security.
- No significant differences were found between those considering leaving and those staying based on teacher characteristics or school settings - suggesting systemic rather than individual issues.

The research problem

Educational systems worldwide are grappling with leadership pipeline challenges, with international organisations documenting widespread recruitment difficulties and diminishing interest in leadership roles.[1] This pattern is evident across the United Kingdom, where studies reveal declining promotion applications and increasing unfilled vacancies, particularly following the pandemic period.[2]

Middle leaders represent a critical but often overlooked cohort within the current leadership crisis. These professionals juggle substantial teaching commitments alongside significant management responsibilities, bridging different organisational levels without the positional authority of senior management. This unique positioning creates distinctive pressures that make understanding their experiences crucial for developing targeted retention strategies.

Research reveals that many middle leaders receive limited preparation for their roles, with leadership development largely self-managed. Pathways to these positions vary considerably, ranging from strategic career planning to unexpected opportunities or senior leader persuasion. [3] The Scottish context intensifies these challenges, as policy aspirations for promoted teachers to lead learning operate against demanding working conditions.

[1] UNESCO (2024) Global education monitoring report, 2024/5, Leadership in education: lead for learning. Paris, UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54676/EFLH5184>. World Bank (2021) Successful Teachers, Successful Students: Recruiting and Supporting Society's Most Crucial Profession. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group

[2] Department for Education (DfE) (2024) Working lives of teachers and leaders: wave 3. London: Government Social Research, <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/working-lives-of-teachers-and-leaders-wave-3>. Dempster G (2024) AHDS Workload Survey 2016-2024. <https://ahds.org.uk/uploads/2016.24-Workload-National.v1.1.pdf>. Aleynikova E, Rostron J, Kitson S, Zuccollo J and Jiménez E (2024) Recruitment and Retention of Senior School Leaders in Wales. Education Policy Institute. <https://epi.org.uk/publications-and-research/recruitment-and-retention-of-senior-school-leaders-in-wales/>

[3] Lipscombe K, Tindall-Ford S, Grice C, De Nobile J. and Davidson J (2025) School middle leadership: aspirations, identification, appointment, development and advancement, International Journal of Educational Management, 39(1), 70-87. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-06-2024-0326>. Grootenboer P, Tindall-Ford S. and Edwards-Groves C (2023) Becoming a middle leader: accidental, aspirational, or anointed, Leading and Managing, 29(1): 43-50. Tang J, Bryant DA and Walker AD (2022) School middle leaders as instructional leaders: building the knowledge base of instruction-oriented middle leadership, Journal of Educational Administration, 60(5)511-526. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-01-2022-0018>.

WHY IT MATTERS

The retention of Principal Teachers has far-reaching implications for Scottish education's capacity to maintain effective school leadership and improvement. Middle leaders serve as the primary talent pool for future senior leaders, making their departure decisions critical to addressing broader leadership succession challenges. Their role as institutional mediators means they absorb systemic pressures that might otherwise impact classroom teachers.

When middle leaders leave or withdraw from leadership aspirations, schools lose crucial capacity for curriculum leadership, teacher mentoring, and pastoral care coordination. The cumulative effect undermines professional capacity in individual schools and across the education system. Given documented recruitment difficulties and declining interest in leadership roles internationally, understanding what drives middle leader turnover becomes essential for maintaining educational quality and continuity.

WHAT HAVE WE LEARNED?

This research reveals a critical situation facing Scotland's middle leaders. More than three-quarters of Principal Teachers surveyed had considered leaving the profession in the past two years (210 among a sample of 273, 77%) - a striking finding that points to systemic problems rather than individual career dissatisfaction.

Four interconnected challenges drive these departure intentions:

Working hours top the list (cited by 87, 41% of those considering leaving), with middle leaders describing their workload as "relentless," "excessive," and "unsustainable." These professionals routinely work far beyond their contracted hours, taking work home most nights and experiencing serious impacts on their physical and mental health.

Analysis revealed seven interrelated causes of extended working hours:

1. Pressure from school leaders or Quality Improvement Officers at local authority level to achieve improved student outcomes
2. Required responses to changing national assessment arrangements
3. Pressure from preparing for or responding to school inspections,
4. Staff absence, under-staffing and staff turnover
5. Expanding job remit without access to specialist support
6. More complex learner needs with declining ring-fenced resource
7. A rise in challenging behaviour among learners, and also parents/carers

Student behaviour issues represent the second major concern, with over one-third of those considering leaving citing what they perceive as declining conduct standards (77, 37%). Principal teachers across school settings reported managing a wide spectrum of challenging behaviours, ranging from developmental issues like poor self-regulation and social-emotional immaturity to more serious conduct problems. These included disrespectful interactions with staff, learning apathy, classroom disruption, and concerning increases in discriminatory and violent behaviours.

Parental engagement has become increasingly challenging according to middle leaders, who report facing unrealistic expectations, hostile communications, and diminishing trust in their professional judgment (31, 15%). Many feel they've become "verbal punch bags" for frustrated parents while lacking adequate backing from senior leadership.

Finally, the **growing complexity of student needs** - including communication, sensory, cognitive, and social-emotional differences - combined with reduced resources, leaves middle leaders feeling unable to provide appropriate support despite increasing expectations for improved outcomes (19, 9%).

For the 23% who intend to stay, their commitment stems from passion for teaching, positive student relationships, and practical considerations like job security and benefits. However, even among this group, many could be characterised as "reluctant stayers" - remaining due to limited alternatives rather than job satisfaction.

The research demonstrates that middle leaders function as institutional dampeners, absorbing pressures that might otherwise impact classroom teachers or senior management. While this protects organisational stability, it places enormous strain on this critical group and threatens the leadership pipeline that school systems depend on.

Voices from the classroom

What middle leaders told us about their working lives

On Overwhelming Workload: "I go in ninety minutes earlier in the morning and often stay two hours later at night. There is still not enough time to stay on top of my tasks by even fifty per cent. When I go home, I don't want to do anything but stay in and go to bed."

"I now stay up late almost every night. I have two young children so I cannot start work until they are in bed. I work from 8pm until 12pm most nights, including weekends, and generally get less than 5 hours sleep."

On Health and Wellbeing Impact: "My physical health and wellbeing are being battered. Even with therapy, which I pay for out of my own pocket, I find that my workload is unsustainable in terms of meeting the needs of all the young people."

"I don't have the ability to leave work at the door. It comes home with me and plays on my mind. I can't switch off. Stress leads to poor sleep."

On Student Behaviour Challenges: "I am regularly verbally abused. I have been hurt in school several times. Filling out violence at work forms has had no impact. Phoning the police has not helped. Staff are absent due to these problems."

"It is simply increasingly dangerous to be in the job. We are failing to support pupils properly through whatever is at the root cause of the behaviour."

On Parental Pressures: "Teachers are being shamed for not being nurturing enough when the reality is it's an easy 'cop out' so SLT (senior leadership team) don't have to challenge parents."

"Many parents opt to shift the blame onto teachers for their children's behaviour or completely ignore the problem."

On Resource Constraints: "I cannot win as there are increasing numbers of pupils with complex additional support needs in the classroom with no support and yet there is an expectation that I raise attainment."

"There are more pupils with learning needs but less support within the classroom, so it rarely feels like I'm actually Getting It Right For Every Child despite every effort being made to do so."

On Staying: "It's the pupils that drive you, the wee gains, the open honesty and the sheer delight in seeing them understand concepts and grow."

"I enjoy my work and consider my role to be important in having an influence on society in the future. The young people I work with are challenging and inspiring and I never have a day when I don't come away having learned something new."

Implications for practice

Why This Matters Now

These findings come at a critical time for Scottish education. As policymakers consider major changes to curriculum, assessment, pupil support, and school inspection systems, the research reveals potential obstacles to successful implementation. When three-quarters of middle leaders are considering leaving, schools may lack the capacity to manage these changes effectively.

Impact on Schools

The constant firefighting mode that middle leaders describe has real consequences for school quality. When Principal Teachers spend their time managing crises rather than focusing on strategic priorities, several important areas suffer. Curriculum development becomes harder to sustain, teacher mentoring becomes less effective, and opportunities to use research to improve practice diminish.

The inability to intervene early with complex student needs creates a vicious cycle - problems escalate, relationships with families deteriorate, and the very support systems schools depend on become strained. This reactive approach often makes existing challenges worse rather than addressing their root causes.

Broader System Effects

Beyond individual schools, these pressures affect how well education policies actually work in practice. When middle leaders lack time and energy for strategic thinking, new initiatives struggle to take root properly. This has knock-on effects for school improvement efforts and makes it harder to develop the next generation of school leaders - fewer teachers seek promotion when they see the toll it takes.

Learning from Other Countries

Scotland's experience reflects challenges seen internationally as teaching becomes more demanding. The research highlights the need for realistic workload models that recognise the challenges facing middle leaders as they balance both teaching and leadership responsibilities effectively. Experience from other education systems suggests that ignoring these practical realities risks undermining both individual leaders and the broader system.

What Needs to Change

The evidence points to the need for comprehensive rather than piecemeal solutions. Rather than expecting individuals to simply cope better with unsustainable demands, the focus should be on improving working conditions systematically. This means addressing workload, behaviour support, parental engagement, and resources in coordinated ways.

Without this kind of systematic approach, schools risk losing not just individual middle leaders, but the institutional knowledge and capacity they represent. The research suggests that sustainable solutions require understanding and addressing the underlying conditions that create these pressures, rather than just treating the symptoms.

How we know this: methodology

This briefing is based on findings from a major national study of teacher workload conducted across Scotland in March 2024. The research surveyed 1,834 teachers from all 32 Scottish local authorities, with 273 Principal Teachers - Scotland's middle leaders - forming the focus of this analysis. Principal teachers in this sample brought substantial classroom experience to their leadership roles, with a median of 17 years of teaching experience. Nearly all participants (n=269, 98%) had taught for five years or more. The demographic and professional characteristics of the sample, including gender distribution, age, and school type broadly aligned with the national profile of Principal Teachers in Scotland.[1]

How We Gathered the Information: Teachers completed an online survey about their working hours and job experiences. We built in several checks to ensure reliable data: we removed any responses that showed implausible weekly working hours, prevented people from completing the survey multiple times, and required answers to all questions before participants could continue. Principal Teachers were asked whether they had considered leaving teaching in the past two years, and to explain their reasons for staying or wanting to leave. Researchers systematically examined all 273 Principal Teacher responses to identify the main factors influencing their career decisions.

The findings presented in this briefing represent the views and experiences of 273 middle leaders across Scotland's school system, providing robust evidence about the challenges facing this critical group in the education workforce. This study was approved by the UWS School of Education and Social Sciences ethics committee, approval number 2024-22252-17355.

[1] Scottish Government (2024) Summary statistics for schools in Scotland 2024. 10 December 2024, <https://www.gov.scot/publications/summary-statistics-for-schools-in-scotland-2024/documents/>

Key supporting research:

Hulme, M., Wood, J., Bignell, C., & Beauchamp, G. (2025). Pressure management: factors influencing the turnover intentions of school middle leaders in Scotland. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17411432251357691>

Hulme, M., Beauchamp, G., Wood, J., & Bignell, C. (2024). *Teacher Workload Research Report 2024*. University of the West of Scotland. <https://www.eis.org.uk/Content/images/Campaigns/QualityEducation/WorkloadResearch.pdf>

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